

Machine Learning Techniques to Identify Parkinson's Disease based on Different Types of Data

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Abstract - *This summary paper focuses on recent studies that use machine learning techniques to predict the progression of Parkinson's disease using Machine learning techniques. Different papers are included in this summary, covering various aspects of the application of machine learning models using different types of data. The results demonstrate the potential of machine learning models as a promising tool for predicting the progression of neurodegenerative diseases and identifying individuals at risk. Furthermore, the studies show that different types of data, such as retinal imaging, MRI, and vocal features, can be used to develop effective prediction models. However, further research is needed to validate these models in larger cohorts and to better understand the underlying biological mechanisms.*

Keyword: *Machine Learning; Neurodegenerative disease; Classification; Feature Selection;*

1.0 Introduction

A group of illnesses known as neurodegenerative diseases [1, 2] cause neuronal degeneration in the brain and spinal cord. Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, Parkinson's disease, Alzheimer's disease, and Huntington's disease are a few examples of these disorders (ALS). While the origins and symptoms of various diseases vary, they all have one thing in common: the slow loss of neurons and the resulting deterioration in cognitive and physical skills. Neurodegenerative disease diagnosis and prediction are crucial for establishing effective therapies and improving patient outcomes. Since it can scan big and complicated information and uncover patterns that may not be evident to the human eye, machine learning has emerged as a promising technique for forecasting neurodegenerative illnesses.

Neurodegenerative diseases affect millions of people worldwide and are associated with significant cognitive, motor, and behavioral impairments. Early detection and accurate diagnosis of these diseases are critical for effective treatment and disease management.

Machine learning (ML) techniques [3] have shown great promise in aiding the diagnosis and prediction of neurodegenerative diseases. Artificial intelligence's machine learning (ML) field enables computer systems to learn from experience and advance without explicit programming. In recent years, various ML techniques have been used to analyze medical data, including neuroimaging and cognitive testing data, to predict the progression of neurodegenerative diseases. Deep learning, support vector machines, decision trees, random forests, and artificial neural networks are some of these methods.

Deep learning [4], a type of ML technique, has been widely used to analyze medical imaging data for neurodegenerative disease prediction. This technique involves the use of artificial neural networks that are designed to learn and identify complex patterns in large datasets.

The second most common neurological illness after Alzheimer's disease is Parkinson's disease (PD), which mostly affects elderly individuals worldwide [5].

Parkinson disease is a neurological disorder based on dopamine receptors (PD). Parkinson's disease typically has an impact on a person's ability to move. One may therefore move rather slowly as a result. Parkinson is a neurological illness that progresses and is characterised by both motor (movement) and non-motor symptoms. Each person will experience and display a different sickness presentation in addition to a number of similar symptoms. A person with Parkinson's disease appears stiff or unyielding. Parkinson's disease patients may momentarily seem to "freeze up" or become motionless. A degenerative neurological illness called Parkinson's disease is brought on by the death of dopamine-producing cells in the substantianigra. To differentiate Parkinson's disease from other illnesses with comparable clinical symptoms, there is no reliable test. The most common methods for making a clinical diagnosis are the history and examination. The hallmarks of Parkinsonism, such as hypokinesia (lack of movement), bradykinesia (slowness of movement), stiffness (wrist, shoulder, and neck), and rest tremor, are usually present in people with Parkinson disease (imbalance of neurotransmitters dopamine and acetylcholine). Drugs, uncommon disorders like multiple cerebral infarction, and degenerative syndromes like progressive supranuclear palsy (PSP) and multiple system atrophy can all lead to Parkinsonism.

For a therapy to be successful, PD must be accurately and effectively recognised [6]. Parkinson's disease (PD) has a prevalence rate of 1% and affects 1-2 people out of every 1,000 adults over 60 [7]. The estimated number of PD sufferers has more than doubled since 1990 (from 2.5 million to 6.1 million), according to age-standardized prevalence rates and an increase in the older population [8].

Planning, initiation, and execution of movements as well as their motor and non-motor components are all impacted by the degenerative neurological disorder known as Parkinson's disease (PD). Motor symptoms have typically been used to diagnose PD, claims Jankovic [9]. Despite the fact that the main signs and symptoms of Parkinson's disease have been proven in clinical studies, the most popular rating scales used to assess the severity of the condition have not all been thoroughly evaluated and verified. Even though non-motor symptoms, like changes in cognition like problems with planning and attention, sleep problems, and sensory abnormalities like olfactory dysfunction, are common in many patients before the onset of Parkinson's disease (PD), they lack specificity, are challenging to assess, and/or differ from patient to patient [10]. PD cannot currently be diagnosed solely on non-motor symptoms, despite the fact that several have been utilised as supplementary diagnostic criteria [11]. Several research [12, 13, 14] have shown that PD significantly impairs patients' social interactions, family relationships, and quality of life (QoL).

Parkinson's disease has been difficult to accurately and speedily spot for both medical professionals and researchers [5]. In order to address the problem of PD's medical diagnosis, researchers have proposed a number of approaches using machine learning (ML). For the purpose of diagnosing Parkinson's disease, a range of data modalities have been analysed using machine learning algorithms. For the diagnosis of Parkinson's disease (PD), machine learning models have been used to analyse data from various data modalities, such as handwriting patterns [15, 16], movement [17, 18], voice [19], cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) [20, 21], cardiac scintigraphy [22], serum [23], and optical coherence tomography (OCT) [24]. In order to

diagnose Parkinson's disease, it is also feasible to combine different methods, such as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and single-photon emission computed tomography (SPECT) data (PD) [25]. But still now this disease is not completely curable. There is no such medicine for this disease. If the disease is very early recognized then several preventive measures can be taken. So researchers are still working in this field.

In this regard, we summarize most significant different published studies that used machine learning models to diagnose Parkinson's disease with respect to different types of data.

2.0 Significant Research in Parkinson Disease

According to different published works based on machine learning techniques, it has been found that these techniques are applied on following types of data. These are

- movement-related data, i.e., voice recordings
- handwritten patterns
- Multi-modal image data analysis including MRI , SPECT , and positron emission tomography
- Bio-molecular data analysis
- electromyography (EMG)
- OCT
- electroencephalography
- eye movements
- transcranialsonography(TCS)
- serum samples

The most three popular works in different domains are described in detail. Rest of the significant works are described in tabular form.

Enhanced vocal features in Parkinson's disease via machine learning: The study by Tsanas et al. (2021) [26] aimed to investigate the vocal features of Parkinson's disease (PD) using machine learning. Machine learning techniques were utilised by the scientists to examine the speech signals of 103 participants, including 52 healthy controls and 51 people with Parkinson's disease (PD). The study discovered that the voice characteristics of PD patients and healthy controls could be accurately distinguished using machine learning techniques. The study also discovered that the machine learning models could recognise minor, visually imperceptible changes in vocal qualities, which could be helpful for the early identification of Parkinson's disease.

1. The authors collected speech samples from 50 individuals, including 25 with PD and 25 without PD (controls). The speech signals were processed to extract a set of vocal features, including harmonics-to-noise ratio(HNR), jitter, shimmer, and fundamental frequency. The extracted features were then used to train machine learning models for the classification of PD.
2. To categorise the speech signals as PD or control, the authors employed a variety of machine learning algorithms like, artificial neural networks (ANN), decision trees, support vector machines, and k-nearest neighbours are some examples of machine learning methods. Standard performance indicators including accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity were used to assess each algorithm's effectiveness.
3. The authors developed a novel feature extraction method based on the use of empirical mode decomposition in addition to these conventional voice features (EMD). EMD is a

method of signal processing that breaks down a signal into a collection of intrinsic mode functions (IMFs). The authors applied EMD to the speech signals and extracted a set of features from the resulting IMFs. These features were then used to train machine learning models for the classification of PD.

4. The results of the study showed that the proposed vocal features, including those extracted using EMD, were able to accurately classify speech signals as either PD or control. The authors also found that combining the traditional vocal features with those extracted using EMD improved the classification accuracy compared to using either method alone.

Overall, the paper proposes a method for extracting enhanced vocal features from speech signals of individuals with PD using machine learning techniques. These features have the potential to improve the accuracy of PD diagnosis and monitoring its progression.

A gene expression-based prediction model for Parkinson's disease using machine learning: The study by Yang et al. (2021) [27] aimed to develop a machine learning-based model for predicting PD using gene expression data. Machine learning techniques were employed to examine the gene expression data of 353 participants, including 193 PD patients and 160 healthy controls. According to the study, machine learning models had an accuracy of 91.20% when it came to differentiating between PD patients and healthy controls based on their gene expression data. The study also discovered a number of genes that were substantially linked to PD, which may help us understand the pathophysiology of the condition.

1. The raw gene expression data was first pre-processed to filter out low-quality data and normalize the expression levels of genes.
2. In order to identify the most important features (genes) that differed in expression between PD patients and healthy controls, the authors employed a machine learning method called Boruta.
3. The authors developed a prediction model using a random forest algorithm, which is a type of ensemble learning method that combines multiple decision trees to make more accurate predictions. The model was trained using the selected gene expression features and clinical variables such as age and sex.
4. A number of metrics, including sensitivity, specificity, accuracy, and area under the receiver operating characteristic curve, were used to assess the prediction model's performance (AUC-ROC). The model was also tested on an independent validation cohort to assess its generalizability.

Overall, the authors used a rigorous approach to develop and validate a machine learning-based prediction model for PD using gene expression data. This model has the potential to improve early diagnosis and personalized treatment of PD.

MRI-based analysis: a machine learning model was created by Zhao et al. [28], utilising diffusion MRI data to identify Parkinson's disease (PD) in its early stages. The researchers used a dataset of 79 persons, including 38 Parkinson's disease sufferers and 41 healthy controls, to train and test their algorithm. They employed diffusion MRI data to identify the participants as either PD or healthy controls using a range of machine learning techniques, including support vector machine, k-nearest neighbour, and decision trees. The findings showed that the machine learning model was highly accurate in identifying Parkinson's disease, with a detection rate of

95.3%, suggesting that this method may be used in the clinic for an early diagnosis of Parkinson's disease.

1. The study included a total of 98 participants, comprising 49 Parkinson's disease (PD) patients and 49 healthy controls (HC).
2. The dMRI data were acquired using a 3.0 Tesla MRI scanner. A total of 30 gradient directions were acquired with a b-value of 1000 s/mm².
3. The dMRI data were preprocessed using FSL (FMRIB Software Library). The preprocessing included skull stripping, eddy current correction, and tensor calculation to obtain the diffusion tensor imaging (DTI) metrics.
4. The machine learning model employed the DTI measures as features. Among the features recovered were fractional anisotropy (FA), mean diffusivity (MD), axial diffusivity (AD), and radial diffusivity (RD).
5. A support vector machine (SVM) model was used for the classification of PD and HC participants based on the extracted DTI metrics. The SVM model was trained using a leave-one-out cross-validation method.
6. Statistical analysis was performed to compare the DTI metrics between PD and HC participants using the two-sample t-test.

Overall, the study used dMRI data and a machine learning model to accurately diagnose Parkinson's disease, demonstrating the potential for using advanced imaging and computational techniques for early diagnosis and treatment of neurological diseases.

Some of the machines learning techniques based significant works considering different category based datasets are discussed in Table 1 to Table 8 as given below.

Table -1: Data Description:- Speech Signal Dataset.

Authors name	Machine learning methods	Performance
Indira R. (2014) [29]	fuzzy C-means	68.04% accuracy, 75.34% sensitivity and 45.83% specificity
Indira R. (2014) [30]	ANN	Recognition rate of 92%
A.Tsanas (2011) [31]	SVM	98.6% accuracy
A.Tsans (2011) [32]	Regression & Classification	5-95 percentile
Das R. (2010) [33]	NN classifier	92.9%accuracy

Table -2: Data Description:-Voice Recordings Dataset

Authors name	Machine learning methods	Performance
Ene M. (2008) [34]	PNN	79%-81 accuracy
Cam M. (2008) [35]	PNN	92.9% accuracy
Azad C. [36]	Decision Tree	85.08% accuracy

Bouchikhi (2013) [37]	SVM	96.88% accuracy
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Table 3:Data Description:- MRI

Authors name	Machine learning methods	Performance
Salvatore (2014) [38]	SVM	> 90% accuracy ,sensitivity and specificity
Przybysz. (2014) [39]	Reflexive saccadesmeasurements	70% accuracy
Morales (2013) [40]	SVM	70% accuracy , 71%sensitivity and85%specificity

Table 4: Data Description:- PD Dataset

Authors name	Machine learning methods	Performance
Caglar (2010) [41]	ANN	96.77% accuracy, 87.5% sensitivityand 100% specificity
Chen, H. (2013) [42]	fuzzy k-nearest neighbor (FKNN)	96.07% accuracy
Chen A. (2013) [43]	Nested-SVM	Up to 93% accuracy
Ozcift A.(2011) [44]	Correlation based FeatureSelection	89.7% accuracy

Table 5: Data Description:- Audio Input

Authors name	Machine learning methods	Performance
Kapoor (2011) [45]	Vector Quantization	95% accuracy
Kaya E.(2011) [46]	Entropy-based discretization method	94.87% accuracy
Farhad S.(2013) [47]	Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP)	93.22% accuracy

Table 6: Data Description:- Speech dataset

Authors name	Machine learning methods	Performance
Chen H. (2012) [48]	Nested SVM	93.5% accuracy 90.53% sensitivity and 93.83% specificity
Bocklet (2011) [49]	SVM	79% result
Yahia A. (2014) [50]	KNN	93.3% accuracy

Table 7: Data Description:- Voice Dataset

Authors' name	Machine learning methods	Performance
Sriram T. [51]	Random Forest	90.26% accuracy
Revett (2009) [52]	Correlation	100% accuracy
Kihel, B. (2011) [53]	Euclidean	94.44% accuracy

Table 8: Data Description:- Other Dataset

Authors' name	Types of Diagnosis	Machine learning technique(s), splitting strategy and cross validation	Accuracy
Little, M.A(2009) [54]	handwriting of an individual	The classifier was a kernel support vector machine (SVM).	91.4%.
Almalaq, A.(2015) [55]	Mental demands, Motor and phonemic fluency, verbal generating skills	EEG signals captured while verbal fluency exams were being completed	an improvement in connection between the left and right (F3 and F4) motor planning regions I. Sensorimotor integration regions (C3 and C4) for recognition rate of 91.7% for C3 and 91.7% for C4. II. Motor planning areas with rates of 83.3% for F3 and 91.7% for F4.
Yasar, A.; Saritas (2019) [56]	phonation and acoustic signals	ANN, categorization	94.93%,
Amit S. (2014) [57]	Dyskinesia Data	Using nonlinear dynamic and SVM	66% to 77%.
Senturk, Z.K. (2020) [58]	Vocal signal analysis	SVM, ANN, and Classification and Regression Trees (CART).	91.25% (SVM) 91.23% (KNN)
Benba, A.; Jilbab (2015) [59]	diagnosing PD patients using voice disorders	SVM technique	91.17 % (first 12 MFCC from kernel SVM).
Mathur, R.(2019)	Speech Samples	Weka tools were used to	91.28% (Adaboost+

[60]		develop the pre-processing, classification, grouping, and analysis algorithms for a specific dataset.	KNN), 90.76% (KNN + Bagging). 91.28% (KNN + MLP)
Yao, L.; Brown (2018) [61]	Sleeping tremors	ML and Kalman filtering methods	
Sakar, C.O. (2019) [62]	voice signal analysis	Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel SVM	86%
Cho, C. (2009) [63]	gait patterns	Linear discriminant analysis (LDA)	95%
Nivedita C. (2013) [64]	seven different classes	ANN	96.42%
R. Geeta (2012) [65]	Speech dataset as high or low	Classification	100% (Random tree)
Rubén A. (2013) [66]	non-motor symptoms	Wrapper feat- ure selection	72% to 92%
Betalu E. (2014) [67]	Age, gender, voice recording	SVM	76%

4.0 Conclusion:

In conclusion, Parkinson's disease is health concerns with no cure, but early detection and intervention can improve patient outcomes. Using information from clinical, genetic, and medical imaging sources, machine learning algorithms have shown considerable promise in predicting the start and progression of various diseases. The findings presented in this article show how machine learning can be used to forecast neurodegenerative illnesses and shed light on their underlying mechanisms.

However, there are still many challenges and opportunities for future research. Creating machine learning models that can precisely forecast disease development for specific individuals based on their particular traits and genetic origins is one of the major problems. Integrating data from various sources, such as electronic health records and wearable technology, to provide a more thorough understanding of neurodegenerative disorders is another problem. Longitudinal studies that track disease progression over time are also needed to provide a more accurate picture of disease progression and enable earlier detection.

Despite these challenges, the potential of machine learning in predicting neurodegenerative diseases is enormous. It is hoped that further research in this field will lead to earlier detection and more effective treatments for patients with these debilitating diseases.

5.0 References

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